

Muskoxen (*Ovibos moschatus*) of Sigguup Nunaa, Greenland: Summary report for 1991-2022

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By

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Raw data for muskox locations, group size and calves are within this report.

Summary (English)

This summary report provides a brief history of the translocation of 31 juvenile muskoxen to the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula in 1992, the results of a minimum count in April 2002, and available post-2002 information.

The April 2002 minimum count observed 193 muskoxen, which included 14 calves (age < 1-year). At 7.25%, the calf percentage was low. Extensive winter ground-icing covering winter pasture in 2001/2002 may have been a major factor. Most muskoxen were observed in the southwest of the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula, i.e. within 40 km of the 1991 release site. Further, most were at elevations below 200 m, which is known to be preferred habitat for muskoxen. Sigguup Nunaa elevations < 200 m involve ca. 1140 km², suggesting that density on lowland habitat was less than 0.2 muskoxen / km².

Following the translocation of muskoxen in 1991, all harvest was prohibited until 2004. That year, a quota of 40 muskoxen was permitted. Since then, quotas and harvested numbers have risen. Recently, it was acknowledged that the Upernavik hunter harvest was more than the reported harvest and possibly 2-3x greater than the permitted quota. Illegal killing has also occurred and may be a substantial source of mortality for the Sigguup Nunaa muskox population. In the year with highest illegal killings, 2021, about 50 muskoxen were wantonly shot and their entire carcasses left in the terrain.

Ad hoc observation in 2002, and post-2002 from locals, suggest the possibility of wolverine (*Gulo gulo*) presence on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula. To date, no reports have been verified. Conclusive documentation may require camera sites and hair snares. A guide for authenticating wolverine tracks is provided in the appendices.

In 1992, muskoxen arrived to Sigguup Nunaa. The single monitoring effort was made in 2002. Although the 2002 count confirmed population growth since their translocation and release in 1991, recent population trend is unknown. Monitoring and assessment are urgently needed for both the muskoxen and their habitat.

Eqikkaaneq (kalaallisut)

Nalunaarusiap eqikkaanertaani oqaluttuarineqarpoq umimmaaqqanik 31-nik Sigguup Nunaanut 1992-mi nuussineq, kiisalu ikinnerpaaffiliilluni kisitsinerup inerneru aprili 2002-meersut, ukiullu tamatuma kingorna paasissutissaatigineqalersut.

Apriliimi 2002mi ikinnerpaaffiliisumik kisitsisoqarmat umimmaat 193it takuneqarput, taakkunanilu piaqqat 14it (ukioq ataaseq uumasimasut) ilanngullugit kisinneqarput. 2001/2002 ukiuunerani sermernartulioaqattaartoqarnerata kingunerisaanik taamak ikitsigisunik piaqqisoqarneranut patsisaasinnaavoq (7,25 procentit). Umimmaat amerlanerpaartaat Sigguup Nunaata kimmut kujasinnerusortaniittut takuneqarput, imaappoq 1991imi nuussiviusumiit 40 km-inik ungasitsigisumiittumi. Amerlanerpaartai 200 m ataallugit qattitsigisumiissimapput, tassa umimmaat uummavigissallugit iluarinerpaasartagaanni. Sigguup Nunaani nuna 1140 km² annertussuseqartoq 200 meterinik qatsinnerusumiissuavoq. Nunap pukkitsortaani umimmaqassuseq taamaasilluni < 0,2 umimmaat/km² iluaniittarput.

Nunap eqqaani najugallit takusinnaasaat malillugit tassa 2022imi kingornalu Sigguup Nunaani qappeqarnissaa (Gulo gulo) naatsorsuutigineqarpoq. Maannamulli uppernarsaataasinnaasumik nalunaaruteqartoqarnikuunngilaq. Nunami assiliissuserneqarnissaa pisariaqarsinnaavoq aammalu meqquminernik naatitsissutaasinnaasumik uppernarsaateqarnissaq anguniarlugu inissiisoqarsinnaassalluni. Qappeqassappat tumaasa uppernarsaatiginissaannut ilitersuut kiggiunneqarsimasunut ilaavoq.

Umimmannik 1992imi nuussisoqarnerata kingorna piniartoqarnissaa 2004 tikillugu inerteqqutaalluinnarsimavoq. Ukioq taanna umimmaat 40it pisassissutigineqarput. Tamatuma kingorna pisassiissutaasut pisarineqartullu amerligaluttuinnarsimapput. Unioqqutitsillunilu pisaqartoqartarnera pisarsimalluni Sigguullu Nunaani umimmannik toqusoqartarsimaneranut tamanna patsisaalluarsinnaalluni. 2021imi umimmaat 50it sorraatsumik aallaaneqariarlutik nunamut qimaannarneqarsimapput, Upernavimmilu pisassiissutaasut marloriaataannikkunik pingasoriaataannik pisaqartoqartarsimassasoq naliliisoqarsimavoq.

Umimmaat Sigguup Nunaanut ukiut 34it matuma siorna nuunneqarput.
Nakkutilliiniarlunilu iliuuserineqartutuaq ukiut 23it matuma siornatigut pisimavoq.
Naallu 2002imi kisitsisoqarnerani 1992imi nuussisoqarnerisa kingorna
amerleriarsimasut kisitsinerup takutikkaluarpa, kingullertigulli qanoq
umimmaqartiginersoq ilisimaneqanngilaq. Umimmaat uumaffiisalu
allaatsinaanneqarnissat misissuiffigineqartarnissaallu
pisariaqartinneqaraluttuinnarpoq.

Resumé (dansk)

Denne sammenfattende rapport fortæller kort om flytningen af 31 unge moskusokser til Sigguup Nunaa-halvøen i 1992, resultaterne af minimumsoptællingen i april 2002 og tilgængelig information efter 2002.

Under minimumsoptællingen i april 2002 observeredes 193 moskusokser, som omfattede 14 kalve (alder < 1 år). Omfattende dannelse af vinteris, der dækkede vintergræsgange i 2001/2002, kan have været en væsentlig faktor til den lave procent af kalve (7,25 %). De fleste moskusokser blev observeret i den sydvestlige del af Sigguup Nunaa-halvøen, dvs. inden for 40 km fra udsætningsstedet i 1991. Desuden var de fleste i højder under 200 m, hvilket er kendt for at være det foretrukne levested for moskusokser. Der er ca. 1140 km² med højder < 200 m på Sigguup Nunaa. Tætheden på lavlandshabitatet var således < 0,2 moskusokser/km².

Lokalbefolkningens ad hoc-observationer i og efter 2002 tyder på mulig tilstedeværelse af jærv (Gulo gulo) på Sigguup Nunaa-halvøen. Til dato er ingen rapporter blevet verificeret. Det kan være nødvendigt med vildtkamera og hårsnarer for at få afgørende dokumentation. En vejledning til at bevise ægtheden af spor af jærv findes i bilagene.

Efter flytningen af moskusokser i 1991 blev al jagt forbudt indtil 2004. Samme år blev en kvote på 40 moskusokser tilladt. Siden da er kvoterne og antallet af nedlagte dyr steget. Ulovlig jagt har fundet sted og kan være en væsentlig kilde til dødelighed i Sigguup Nunaa-moskusoksebestanden. I 2021 blev omkring 50 moskusokser hensynsløst skudt og efterladt i terrænet, og antallet af nedlagte dyr i Upernavik blev vurderet til ofte at være 2-3 større end kvoten.

For 34 år siden ankom moskusokser til Sigguup Nunaa. Den eneste overvågningsindsats fandt sted for 23 år siden. Selvom optællingen i 2002 bekræftede bestandstilvækst siden flytning og udsætning i 1991, er den seneste bestandsudvikling ukendt. Der er et presserende behov for overvågning og assessment af både moskusokserne og deres levesteder.

Sigguup Nunaa muskoxen: a translocated population

Figure 1. Map of Sigguup Nunaa (Svartenhuk Halvø) peninsula, Avannaata municipality, Greenland, illustrating the study boundary (area ca. 4150 km²), two cabins, and the 1991 location (red star) where the translocated 31 juvenile muskoxen were released in the bottom of Arfertuarssuk Fjord.

Muskoxen (*Ovibos moschatus* Zimmermann) were never native to the Sigguup Nunaa (Svartenhuk Halvø) peninsula (71°49'N, 54°25'W), which is currently within the Avannaata municipality of northwestern Greenland. Historically, muskoxen inhabited only Greenland's north and northeast coasts. Today's population of muskoxen on Sigguup Nunaa began in the summer of 1991, when 31 juveniles (21 females, 10 males) were ear tagged and translocated to the peninsula, a Government of Greenland decision. Sigguup Nunaa was one of many Greenland sites that received translocations of muskox in the latter half of the 20th century (Appendix 1). The Sigguup Nunaa release location was in the bottom of the Arfertuarssuk Fjord (Fig. 1). The juveniles were captured from the Maniitsoq muskox population near the Kangerlussuaq (Søndre Strømfjord) international airport at ca. 67°N. The Maniitsoq population itself was the result of translocations in the 1960's (Cuyler et al. 2022).

Hunting on Sigguup Nunaa was prohibited until 2004, and prior to 1991 large predators had been absent from the region for decades.

Already just one year after translocation, in 1992, two newborn calves were observed. Although not systematically monitored, beginning in 1995, sporadic observations were provided by Air Greenland pilots flying over the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula (Peter Nielsen pers comm) (Table 1). Locations accompanied the four observations in 1999. One February group of 19 animals was in the southwest corner of the peninsula in the Maligíssap kúa river valley (place names in Appendix 2). A second February group of 11 muskoxen was on the east side of the peninsula between the Firefjeld highlands and the Uiarsaariaq valley, which is immediately south of Firefjeld. A third February group of 21 was in the Uligssat qôruat valley, which is the farthest east of all the valleys along the south coast. Later, in July 1999, a group of 10 muskoxen, which included four calves, was observed near Maligíssap tasíngortarssuit, which is the area at the mouth of the Maligíssap kúa river near Svartenhavn (Black Harbour) and Posthusnæs. These observations indicate some calving success and growth in population size.

Table 1. Number of muskoxen observed on Sigguup Nunaa from 1991 to 2000.

Year	Month/Season	Muskox number	Comments
1991	Summer	31	Translocated juveniles
1992	Summer	-	Two calves observed
1995	April	36	Included six (6) calves
1998	Autumn	57	-
1999	February	51	Three groups, numbering 19, 11, & 21
1999	July	10	Included four (4) calves
2000	-	68	-

This is a summary report of the muskox population inhabiting the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula over the period 1991 – 2022. The report also evaluates possible wolverine presence on the peninsula. The information is a collaborative effort involving Pinngortitaleriffik – Greenland Institute of Natural Resources (GINR) and the Avannaata (Upernavik) municipality.

The 2002 minimum count

Figure 2. The snowmobile routes used for the April 2002 ground-based minimum count of muskoxen on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula.

The ground-based 2002 muskox minimum count on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula used four snowmobiles, each driven by one of the count participants: C. Cuyler, Aaron II Karlsen, Roberth Jovassen, Jens Peter Jørgensen. In total, the count required 11 days of travel. Two days were required for the return-trip between the town of Upernavik and the settlement of Upernavik Kujalleq, (ca. 100 km each way). Sigguup Nunaa was accessible from the latter. Counting muskoxen used a total of nine days over the 06-22 April period (Fig. 2). Most of the count occurred from 06 to 12 April (both days included) with further effort on the 16th and 22nd of April. During the initial week of counting, a total of ca. 1200 km was driven. The average snowmobile travelling speed while driving between observed muskox groups was ca. 30-40 km/hr. Several consecutive nights were spent in the field. Four nights were spent in two cabins (Fig.

1) on the peninsula. Although other cabins existed, there were only two that were inhabitable in winter. Further to the two cabins, participants overnighted once in Nuugaatsiaq and two nights in Upernavik Kujalleq. Details regarding methods are in Appendices 3 and 4.

Muskox feeding sites

During the count effort, a blizzard on 06 April 2002 removed most of the evidence for past muskoxen feeding sites. However, we observed and recorded positions for several sites where muskoxen had recently dug into the snow making craters to access forage vegetation (Fig. 3). Vegetation remaining inside the feeding craters was various combinations of dwarf willow (*Salix herbacea*), dwarf birch (*Betula nana*), grasses (Fam. Gramineae), sedges (*Carex sp.*), berries (*Vaccinium sp.*) and lichens (including *Cetraria spp.*).

Figure 3. Observed muskox feeding sites (⊙), April 2002, on the Siggup Nunaa peninsula, Greenland.

We observed that muskoxen could remain foraging in one area for several days, i.e. on the south-facing windswept slopes north of the Maligissap kûa river (grid cell S_8). Although the slopes were predominantly bare rock-strewn ground, where snow was scarce and often lacked depth, the slopes had been grazed by muskoxen from top to bottom and seemingly along the entire width (Fig. 4). Foraging over an entire area was also apparent on the eastern side of the Mitdlôrfik Fjord.

Figure 4. Combination of snow cover and bare ground typical of the windswept hillslopes north of the Maligissap kûa river, where muskox feeding sites were observed, April 2002, Sigguup Nunaa, Greenland.

Muskoxen

15 groups of muskoxen were observed, for a total of 193 animals (Table 2). The total included 14 calves born in the spring of 2001, i.e. age < 1-year. The remaining 179 muskoxen were aged > 1-year. Calves were 7.25 % of the total observed. Although the 2002 minimum count employed only two age classes, we observed four animals of medium body size that could not be calves or adults. These were likely yearlings or 2-year-olds. Note that groups numbered 13 and 14 were observed on the 16th of April by a local hunter, Karl Kristian Kruse, who was on a polar bear hunting trip along the Sigguup Nunaa coast. Further, on the 22nd of April, study observers Aaron II Karlsen and Roberth Josvassen drove up the Umiarfik Fjord (that had not been counted earlier) to check the shorelines for muskoxen. On the north shore, they observed two muskoxen, which became group number 15 in the minimum count.

Figure 5. Consecutive locations (♦) where muskox groups were observed on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula, in the period 06 to 22 April 2002.

13 out of the 15 groups of muskoxen were observed in the southwest of the study area and within 40 km of the 1991 release location (Fig. 1, 5). Those 13 groups totaled 178 muskoxen, 92% of all observed. Further, 11 out of the 15 groups of muskoxen were observed at lowland elevations below 200 m (Table 2, Fig. 5). Those 11 groups totaled 140 muskoxen, 71% of the observed. None were observed at elevations over 300 m.

The early April count was 193 muskoxen, which must not be confused with an estimate of muskox population size for the entire Sigguup Nunaa peninsula. 193 is just the number of muskoxen observed. In the 11 years since 31 juveniles were released in 1991, this constitutes an over 6-fold growth in population size. Despite growth, the rough (just two age categories) April 2002 herd structure observed a low percentage of calves, 7.25% (14 calves out of a total of 193 muskoxen). This suggests either possible poor calf production in the spring of 2001 or low calf survival over the winter 2001-2002. Alternatively, a combination of both may have occurred. Poor forage availability

is among the factors that can reduce winter calf survival. In April 2002, thick ground-ice covered much of the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula and was likely an effective barrier to foraging with negative consequences for calf survival. For caribou and muskoxen, extreme rain-on-snow and ice-locked pastures can drive mortality events (Kohler & Aanes 2004, Jenkins et al. 2011) and have led to severe population crashes (Hansen et al. 2019). Regardless, the low calf percentage, 7.25%, observed in 2002 cannot have been typical for the 1992-2001 period, or the observed 6-fold growth in population size would not have been possible.

Table 2. Results of the 2002 muskox minimum count on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula.

Date	Group ID #	Group Size	Calf Number	Grid cell ID	Longitude (DD.ddd)	Latitude (DD.ddd)	Elevation (m)
06-Apr-02	1	7	1	N_6	-55,3261663	71,8314247	ca. 100
06-Apr-02	2*	17	0	S_8	-55,0634641	71,6437476	ca. 250
07-Apr-02	3	16	1	S_5	-55,4120230	71,6478265	ca. 250
07-Apr-02	4	16	0	S_7	-55,1605715	71,6461915	ca. 250
07-Apr-02	5	4	0	V_6	-55,2103733	71,5316930	ca. 200
07-Apr-02	6	2	0	V_6	-55,2146185	71,5235244	ca. 150
07-Apr-02	7	3	0	V_6	-55,2313917	71,5195001	ca. 125
08-Apr-02	8	20	3	Y_9	-54.8684822	71.4155216	ca. 100
10-Apr-02	9	5	0	O_18	-53.8290878	71.7726416	ca. 100
11-Apr-02	10**	8	0	S_16	-54,1334579	71,6559917	ca. 100
11-Apr-02	11	11	0	Q_9	-54.9260655	71.7060999	ca. 150
11-Apr-02	12	38	5	O_4	-55.4811520	71.7728885	ca. 150
16-Apr-02	13	11	4	X_4	-55,5094705	71,4737805	ca. 100
16-Apr-02	14	33	0	Y_4	-55,4580947	71,4519440	ca. 100
22-Apr-02	15	2	0	K_8	-55.0524468	71.9342856	ca. 50
	SUM	193	14				

* One muskox had ear tags. Age was 12 years because it was one of the translocated yearlings in 1991.

** 60 cm deep powder snow, where this group was foraging, initially obscured that they were standing up.

Miscellaneous animal sightings or tracks

On 05 April, while travelling over the sea ice from Upernavik to Upernavik Kujalleq, one seal (Fam. Pinnipedia) was lying on the ice. On the return to Upernavik, 13 April, four seals were observed on the ice. Species were not ascertained.

Regarding the study area, beyond muskoxen, no other animals were sighted except birds, i.e., three ptarmigan (*Lagopus mutus*) and two ravens (*Corvus corax*). However, several different animal tracks were seen. Tracks from one Arctic fox appeared in Tasiussaqa valley and several of the other four valleys on the south coast. Like the fox, Arctic hare tracks were regularly observed inside the five river valleys of the southern coast. Hare tracks were also observed on the central east side of the peninsula in the

lowlands east of Firefield, inside the Kugssinerssuaq valley (north of Kanglussaq imâ Bay) and the Qordlortûp kûa river valley. Arctic hare had also made regular use of the underside of the Arfertuarssuk Fjord cabin. Fresh polar bear tracks came out from the Tasiussaq valley onto the Tasiussap imâ sea ice. The bear tracks came over the highlands that separated the Tasiussaq valley from the next valley to the east. Subsequent examination of the next valley revealed that the bear had descended from the glaciated mountain tops at the north end of that valley.

Figure 6. Photographs of the unknown animal track observed deep in the Qordlortuup kûa river valley, east side of the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula, 10 April 2002. Length of paw print (left photo) was 8 cm, from toe-tip to rear of chevron (Δ) shaped foot pad.

Unknown animal tracks

On a hard snow substrate, tracks made by an unknown animal (Fig. 6) were observed deep inside the Qordlortûp kûa river valley, on the central east side of the peninsula at approximately 54.322° W and 71.782° N. The tracks followed the river and led further north into the valley. Although initially speculated to be wolverine, the two photographs taken do not show the claw marks, second rear heal pad, or the 5th toe characteristic of wolverine paw prints. Meanwhile, the length of the paw print (sans claws or rear heal pad), asymmetric toe pattern and chevron (Δ) shaped foot pad were somewhat reminiscent of wolverine. The track sequence of 'sets' of paw prints was not recorded, photographed or described.

Snow & ice

In April 2002, snow conditions were highly variable. Snow depth on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula could be 1 meter and consist completely of powder snow. Most of the five valleys along the south coast were covered in such deep powder snow, so much so that the snowmobiles wallowed through, often tipping over. Deep powder was prevalent on the east side of the peninsula, specifically on the fjord ice of the bays, Umîvîup kangerdlua (Kanglussap imâ) and Kanglussap imâ. In the former, the powder snow hid underlying slush/ice, which slowed driving, and obscured dangerous holes in the sea ice. The latter were detected by a slight dip in the powder snow covering. The 1 m deep powder also covered the broad valley between Firefjeld and Itsako mountains. Even deeper powder covered the Kugssinerssuaq valley. Another valley, the Kangiussap kûa, was impossible to enter because of too much powder snow. The powder snow depth, which was $\geq 1\text{m}$, was impossible for the snowmobiles to drive through. Only one snowmobile had the necessary gear, which were extra wide plastic skis that attached onto the bottom of the snowmobile's usual metal skis (Appendix 5). These allowed that snowmobile to 'surf' through the powder snow and make a pathway for the three others to follow, albeit wallowing their way through. At other times, the snow surface was windblown and rock-hard, e.g. in the "pass" between the Amitsup kûa and Maligíssap valleys. In the Usuit kûgssuat valley, the snow was windblown, which made the surface hard enough for driving snowmobiles upon. If walking, however, the surface broke and you sank into it. Rivers could present difficult conditions for snowmobile driving because the river ice was often covered by a layer of water/slush or to lack ice completely. Also, the lack of ice on rivers was sometimes dangerously hidden under a layer of deep powder snow. Regardless, sufficient speed was necessary to avoid sinking into the rivers with snowmobiles and sledges. Finally, the sea ice between Upernavik and Upernavik Kujalleq was unreliable, specifically between islands. Also, by mid-April snowmobile sea ice travel was impeded by unexpected ice breakup, open sea water and excessive screw-ice (Appendix 6).

Winter ground-icing – ice-locked pastures

Over the count effort area, regardless of route taken, much of the ground surface was covered by a layer of ice that was 5-10 cm thick, e.g. this winter ground-icing covered the Amitsup kûa valley, entire Narssaq lowlands and everywhere we drove on the eastern side of the peninsula. The ice was caused by a rainstorm event that affected the entire Upernavik district on the 20th of December 2001 (Aaron II Karlsen, pers

comm). Frozen water overflow, apparent throughout the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula, even up the mountainsides (Fig. 7), may have been the result of that winter rain event.

Figure 7. Frozen water overflow on the mountainsides and on rivers was common in early April 2002 on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula. Photo by C. Cuyler.

Information from the 2004-2022 harvest data

Commercial & sport harvest

Muskox hunting was prohibited on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula, from their release in 1991 until and including 2003. Hunter harvest began in 2004 with a quota of 40 muskoxen. The Government of Greenland manages harvest seasons and quotas. Initially, the Directorate for Environment and Nature (DMN) was involved but now decisions are made by the Department of Fisheries & Hunting (APN).

The 2004 hunting season was from 01 August to 20 September, and both commercial and sport hunters were advised to take bulls. This also applied to the 2005 hunting season. In 2006, the government raised the annual quota to 60 muskoxen, based on local knowledge that the muskoxen were expanding northward toward the town of Upernavik, which suggested abundance was increasing (DMN, Jørgen Søholm pers

comm). The hunting season (1 Aug. – 20 Sept.) remained unchanged until at least 2010. Commercial hunters received the largest share of annual quotas and reported harvests reflect this difference (Table 3). Since hunting began in 2004, quotas and reported harvest increased (Fig. 8). In the period 2015-2022 the combined sport and commercial harvest quota for muskoxen on Sigguup Nunaa was 150 animals and the harvest season was from 01 August to 15 October, both dates included. Trophy bulls and cows with calf-at-heel were forbidden for sport and commercial harvest. Since 2004, the quota has remained evenly divided between the Upernavik and Ummannaq management areas. The Government of Greenland website, www.sullissivik.gl contains some information on harvest regulations.

Figure 8. Reported combined sport and commercial harvest of muskoxen on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula in the 2004-2022 period. The drop in harvest number for 2022 is suspected owing to incomplete reporting. Data unavailable for 2017.

Trophy harvest

Since 2007 the possibility of trophy hunting has been permitted and allocated a small annual quota, which could be fulfilled over the summer and winter season (Table 4), however, trophy quotas may never have been utilized. To date, the trophy hunting industry for Sigguup Nunaa has yet to develop, e.g. in 2024 there was no trophy hunting activity (Nuka M. Lund pers comm).

Table 3. Government of Greenland muskox quotas and reported harvest for sport and commercial hunters from the Upernavik & Uummannaq regions.

Year	Harvest Quota	Total Reported Harvest ¹	Upernavik harvest		Uummannaq harvest	
			Sport	Commercial	Sport	Commercial
2004	40	36	0	17	3	16
2005	40	46	8	15	3	20
2006	60	54	4	21	12	17
2007	50	47	4	19	7	17
2008	50*	44	5	20	4	15
2009	48	48	3	19	4	22
2010	70*	73	4	33	9	27
2011	70	61	5	19	4	33
2012	70	52	4	21	4	23
2013	70	64	5	29	7	23
2014	70	98	6	57	11	24
2015	82	80	8	29	7	36
2016	150	109	7	52	5	45
2017	150	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable
2018	150	98	8	45	10	35
2019	150	123	9	47	6	61
2020	150	118	8	42	20	48
2021	150	131	9	55	14	53
2022 ^a	150	85	11	38	6	30
SUM	1920	1367	108	578	136	545

¹ The Government of Greenland harvest data is not associated with the population from which the animal is shot. Instead, harvest is associated with the hunter's address. Since hunters can travel and take animals from several populations, the reported harvest in the above table may include muskoxen from other populations than Sigguup Nunaa, e.g. 2005, 2010, and 2014 quotas versus reported harvest.

* Likely quota for given year when documentation was not available.

^a 2022 harvest may yet be incompletely reported.

Table 4. Government of Greenland quotas and seasons for trophy hunting of muskoxen on Sigguup Nunaa. Upernavik & Uummannaq regions, despite the trophy hunting industry remaining undeveloped. When data was unavailable, the cells are blank.

Year	Trophy Quota	Trophy Season	
		summer	winter
2007	10	1 Jul – 15 Oct	11 Mar – 11 Apr
2008			
2009	12	1 Jul – 15 Oct	11 Mar – 11 Apr
2010	12	1 Jul – 15 Oct	11 Mar – 11 Apr
2011	12	1 Jul – 15 Oct	11 Mar – 11 Apr
2012	12	1 Jul – 15 Oct	11 Mar – 11 Apr
2013	12	1 Jul – 15 Oct	11 Mar – 11 Apr
2014	12	1 Jul – 15 Oct	11 Mar – 11 Apr
2015	12	1 Jul – 15 Oct	11 Mar – 11 Apr
2016-2020	12	unavailable	unavailable
2021	12	01 Aug – 31 Oct	15 Feb – 10 Mar
2022	12	01 Aug – 31 Oct	15 Feb – 10 Mar
2023	12	01 Aug – 31 Oct	15 Feb – 10 Mar
2024	12	01 Aug – 31 Oct	15 Feb – 10 Apr

Illegal harvest

Over the years, illegal harvesting was reported. Sometimes animals were shot, and the entire carcass, or portions thereof, just left in the terrain to rot.

In the summer of 2002 (same year as the minimum count described in this report), six muskoxen were shot on the shores of Umîvîup Kangerdlua Fjord, on the east side of the peninsula. Only the hind legs had been removed from the carcasses. Members of the Nuugaatsiaq settlement were responsible (Nuugaatsiaq, anon pers comm). That same summer, a further two kills were suspected, and several crippled muskoxen were observed hobbling on the shores of the Umîvîup Kangerdlua Fjord.

In 2003, an illegal harvest was again reported of four or five muskoxen shot on the eastern side of Sigguup Nunaa by members of the Nuugaatsiaq settlement (Nuugaatsiaq, anon pers comm). This event was reported to the police.

In September 2015, the Upernavik hunting officer, Niels E. P. J. Hansen, discovered 13 muskoxen that had been shot illegally on the west side of Sigguup Nunaa, directly south of the Upernavik Kujalleq settlement. The carcasses were found ca. 5 km from the coast and spread over a ca. 50 m area on a hill slope. There were three untouched adult carcasses that were left to rot in the terrain (Fig. 11). The remaining ten were small-bodied calves and juveniles that had been skinned and their heads scattered about.

In 2021, in the southern portion of Sigguup Nunaa, ca. 50 muskoxen were illegally shot. All were left rotting in the terrain. On the 16th of August 2021, the website for the Government of Greenland (<https://naalakkersuisut.gl>), published the news that at least 20 muskoxen were killed illegally on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula and the carcasses untouched. The 2021 killings and those in 2015 are classed as wanton killings rather than harvest. The 2021 carcasses were found inside three fjords, Arfertuarssuk, Mitdlôrfik and Amitsup suvdlua. Using a helicopter to fly over the south portion of Sigguup Nunaa, the local hunting officer and Greenland police investigated. They observed ca. 50 carcasses and a total of only seven live muskoxen (Nuka Møller Lund pers comm). If found, the perpetrator(s) would have faced the possibility of a fine, confiscated boat/firearm and loss of hunting license. No arrests were forthcoming. In response to the above news, the president of a local chapter of the Greenland Hunter's Union (KNAPK) in Avannaata appeared on Qanorooq (Greenland National Television evening news) and said Upernavik hunters typically shoot two to three

muskoxen per hunting license, rather than just the one permitted. Besides illuminating poor hunter compliance with regulations, his statement suggested illegal harvesting was common and amounted to 2-3 times the government quota for Upernavik. GINR responded with the recommendation that documentation be obtained for how many muskoxen were shot annually and the health/body condition of those harvested. Further, GINR suggested asking for the local hunters' opinion regarding muskox population size, whether population growth was occurring, and if the muskox harvest quota was reasonable in relation to population size. To date, this information remains to be obtained.

Figure 9. Harvest quota and reported harvest of muskoxen from the Sigguup Nunaa muskox population, now with total numbers of muskoxen removed when illegal harvest and/wanton killings are added.

Although Figure 9 provided information about the reported harvest. This is not the total number of muskoxen removed annually because illegal harvest and wanton killings occur. The total number of muskoxen removed annually from the Sigguup Nunaa muskox population often exceeded permitted quota when illegal harvest and wanton killing (shot and left to rot) are added to the reported legal harvest (Fig. 10). Given the suggestion that Upernavik hunters typically shoot two to three muskoxen per hunting license and assuming the illegal harvest for the Upernavik half of the annual harvest is just double the Upernavik reported catch and applies to only 2020, 2021 and 2022, then true harvest may be at least an additional 50, 64 and 49 animals respectively. When wantonly killed animals are added (13 in 2015; ca. 50 muskoxen in 2021) into the appropriate year, then the total removed became 93 in 2015 and 245 in 2021.

Figure 10. One of the three adult muskoxen shot illegally and left to rot in the terrain on the west side of Sigguup Nunaa in 2015. Photo by Niels Hansen, hunting officer Upernavik.

Wolverine presence - unverified

Although there are wolverines on Ellesmere Island, Canada, there are few historical reports of wolverine in Greenland, and these consist of only track sightings in the nearby Thule region during the 1930s and 1940s (Glass et al. 2022). The Greenland reports were never verified by photographs, but the sheer volume of reports suggests wolverine were occasional visitors to Thule (Muus et al 1981, Glass et al. 2022). Given the lack of reports over the latter half of the 20th century, in 1991 (translocation year, and the decade thereafter) it was assumed that there were no large predators on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula, polar bears notwithstanding. However, during the muskox minimum count of April 2002 tracks of an unknown animal were observed. At the time of sighting (10th of April 2002), the tracks were suspected of being wolverine (*Gulo gulo*). Upon further examination, the identification of the unknown track was inconclusive. Among other characteristics, individual wolverine tracks

typically show five toes arranged in an unsymmetric pattern, exhibit claw marks and a heel/foot (Appendix 7). In contrast, the photographs of the unknown animal's track clearly showed just four toes. Since it is possible that the substrate was too hard to permit wolverine characteristics to appear in the paw-print, positive identification would have required more and better photos of individual paw prints and specifically sets of the animal's track sequence. These were not provided, so the presence of wolverine was not confirmed.

Following the unknown animal tracks observed during the April 2002 muskox count, there were unconfirmed reports of possible wolverine or their tracks in Sigguup Nunaa. Already in early June 2002, a hunter from Uummanaq took photos of what he thought were wolverine paw-prints in the snow. These photos subsequently appeared in a news broadcast by Greenland National Television (KNR) stating they were wolverine. However, when GINR's wolverine specialist, Arild Landa, examined the photos, the indistinct and incomplete paw-prints did not permit conclusive identification.

On 8-9 September 2003, Remy Jensen, a long-time resident of the Nuugaatsiaq settlement and manager of the power station, was staying at his cabin, which was located on the south shore of Umiviuup Kangerdlua Fjord, on the east side of Sigguup Nunaa. Late in the evening of the 8th of September, Remy and his guests heard a loud commotion erupt from a large assembly of geese, which were resting on the fjord shore some kilometers west from his cabin. The following day everyone went to investigate. They found animal tracks in the low tide zone that were from two individuals of the same species. Both tracks had simultaneously crept up to where the geese had been, and both tracks illustrated an attack on the geese. The tracks were measured, and an individual paw print was ca. 10 cm in length, which included the claws, while width was ca. 7 cm. Further, many of the tracks illustrated marked heels. When asked whether there were four or five toes, Remy was uncertain, but thought he remembered five toes. No one had a camera, so no photographs were taken. Remy and his two companions followed the unknown tracks for some distance along the shore and saw more tracks of the same animal. For comparison, smaller Arctic fox tracks were also present in abundance along the shore. The measured size of the paw prints specifically precludes Arctic foxes having made the tracks. While a marked heel suggests the possibility of wolverine, the width and length of the paw prints also match the size-range for wolves (*Canis lupus*), wolverines and some sled dogs (*Canis*

lupus familiaris). Without more information or photographs, the presence of wolverine could not be confirmed.

Further south of Sigguup Nunaa, reports of strange animals or their tracks also came from the Uummannaq and Ilulissat regions. In August, two photos of one indistinct paw print set in soft soil were sent to GINR from Uummannaq. Despite the long claws, only four toes were apparent. On soft substrates, a wolverine's five toes are expected to show. Further, the size of the paw print was unknown and nothing in the photo provided scale. Thus, the photos did not permit verification as wolverine. In October 2010, near the Uummannaq airport on the north side of the Nuussuaq Halvø peninsula, hunters from Qaarsut took photographs of something that they believed was a wolverine moving <50 m from the shore where a road leads to some old boring holes (Anthon Zeeb, hunting officer pers comm). Unfortunately, those photos never materialized for examination. The following year, in early April 2011, GINR received photos of what were believed to be wolverine tracks in the Ilulissat, Disko Bay area. However, the individual tracks were dog-like, and the poor quality of the photos did not permit conclusive identification.

Thus, wolverine (*Gulo gulo*) presence on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula is as yet undocumented and remains to be proven. Conclusive documentation for the presence of wolverine on Sigguup Nunaa, or elsewhere in Greenland, may require baited camera sites providing photo evidence. These can be combined with hair snares to collect material for genetics analyses.

Monitoring recommendations

Muskoxen are characteristically sedentary and generally forage in low lying valleys and coastal areas (Nellemann & Reynolds 1997, Reynolds et al. 2002, Gustine et al. 2011, Nellemann 2011, Anderson & Ferguson 2016, Schmidt et al. 2016). Optimal muskoxen habitat appears to be below 200 m elevation, with elevations below 100 m supporting the highest densities of muskoxen (Thomas et al. 1981). The above is supported by the results of the Sigguup Nunaa minimum count in 2002. All 31 translocated juveniles were released inside the Arfertuarssuk Fjord, which is in the southwest of the peninsula. The 2002 count illustrated that 11 years later most (92%) of the muskoxen observed were within 40 km of the release site, indicating little

expansion in distribution. Regarding lowlands, 71% of all muskoxen observed were grazing at elevations under 200 m. Highland elevations > 300 m were not used.

On the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula, lowland elevations under 200 m comprise about ca. 1140 km². Applying the minimum count of 193 muskoxen, the 2002 stock density on the Sigguup Nunaa's lowlands was ca. < 0.2 /km². Although lowlands comprise just 27% of the total area and there is no information regarding vegetation (quantity, quality, and availability) and range condition, the low stocking density in 2002 suggests that 193 muskoxen were not likely a problem for either. During the 2002 count, the feeding sites observed ad hoc may yet provide preliminary information as to which Sigguup Nunaa vegetation communities are important for the muskoxen in late winter.

Despite collaboration between locals and GINR with the intention to conduct minimum counts in the years since the first and only count in 2002 (Appendix 8), there have been none. Although there were plans for monitoring in 2008, 2011 and 2012. In 2008 and 2012, funding was not forthcoming. In 2011, an unexpected fisheries situation arose. This prevented the Upernavik hunting officer from initiating the muskox count because fish-catch inspections took priority. Regardless, even in 2019 local interest remained for renewed collaboration and a new minimum count (Niels Hansen pers comm).

In the summer of either 2019 or 2020, a video obtained by drone near Upernavik Kujalleq, Sigguup Nunaa, illustrated one group of 14 muskoxen, which included five calves (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eWnst9FFB3Y>). In addition to the five calves, the group structure included three adult bulls, one juvenile bull (age ca. 2½ years) and five adult cows (one aged 3-years, four of age > 3-years). Although a calf percentage of 36% seems excellent, consider that the group lacked juveniles (excepting one). Albeit just one group of muskoxen, this suggests calf survival to maturity may be difficult. If true, causes could be many and would include juvenile targeted hunter harvest and adverse environmental conditions.

Currently, the muskox population on Sigguup Nunaa is assumed to be well-established. Still, Sigguup Nunaa received its muskoxen 34 years ago. The one monitoring effort, a minimum count, happened 23 years ago. Monitoring and assessment are long overdue, and currently the annual number of muskoxen killed may be 2-3 times greater than the permitted quota. Good harvest and management

decisions are data-based, but data for Sigguup Nunaa is lacking. New muskox population monitoring is essential. At the least, it must include abundance, herd structure and health. Further, the lack of knowledge regarding Sigguup Nunaa habitat must be remedied. Vegetation mapping and an assessment of range quality and total area are urgently needed. Finally, what is the true annual harvest? Open two-way discussions with local hunter unions might facilitate future collaborations for gathering local knowledge, improving compliance with harvest regulations, and bringing about future counts or surveys.

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Appendix 1
Muskox populations in Greenland

Figure 11. Muskox populations in Greenland. Native populations (blue) are in North and Northeast Greenland. The west has several translocated populations (orange) or those resulting from range expansion (green). Population borders are approximations and size does not reflect animal abundance. National Park in northeast Greenland is indicated with stippling and muskoxen inhabit most of the vegetated coastal areas.

Appendix 2

Place names (official and unofficial) commonly used in the Avannaata municipality & Sigguup Nunaa (Svartenhuk Halvø) peninsula

Names provided in this report are taken from maps using archaic spelling norms for the Greenlandic language (Kalaallisut). Field work was based on these maps.

The maps were produced by Tage Schjøtt, Kort- og Matrikelstyrelsen, Denmark:

- Published 1992, Nunavik [Svartenhuk] (A66/90), 1:250,000
- Published 1992, Upernavik [Upernavik] (A66/90), 1:250,000

In the 1970's, the Government of Greenland legislated new spelling norms, but implementation has been slow. Official place names (new spelling) can be found here:

<https://www.arcgis.com/apps/View/index.html?appid=c5c7d9d52a264980a24911d7d33914b5>

Note: to see names on the map, zoom in until displayed scale bar indicates 0-3 km.

Figure 12. Overview of major place names for the Avannaata (Upernavik) municipality and Sigguup Nunaa peninsula. Elevations under 200 m are green, those above 200 m are pale yellow. Glaciers and Ice Cap are white.

Appendix 4

Methods for the 2002 minimum count

Facilitation of community-based muskox minimum count

On 03 April 2002, a GINR research scientist, Dr. Christine Cuyler, travelled to Upernavik to meet with community members on 04 April for an exchange of information and to finalize all details of the proposed April 2002 minimum count of muskoxen on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula. The meeting was attended by Jens Immanuelson (Mayor), Julianne Sørensen (Municipal Director), Nikolaj Jensen (Business Manager), Aaron II Karlsen (Commercial Hunter, Upernavik Kujalleq), Roberth Josvassen (Commercial Hunter, Upernavik Kujalleq), Jens Peter Jørgensen, "Aqqaluk" (Upernavik Hunting Officer for Greenland Fisheries and License Control (GFLK)), and C. Cuyler (GINR). Aaron II Karlsen, Roberth Josvassen, and Jens Peter Jørgensen, were chosen by the Upernavik leadership to participate in the field work and become acquainted with muskox minimum count methods.

Study area

Aside from the translocated population of muskoxen, native wild mammals present on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula were the arctic hare (*Lepus arcticus* Rhoads), arctic fox (*Vulpes lagopus* Linnaeus), and a vestigial presence of native caribou (*Rangifer tarandus groenlandicus*). Large mammalian predators were absent at the time of translocation. Albeit polar bears (*Ursus maritimus*) were known to frequent coastal sea ice in winter.

Although there are several settlements and one town in the Avannaata municipality (all of which are on islands), there are no permanent human habitations in the study area of the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula. The nearest settlement, Nuugaatsiq (84 inhabitants), is 24 km distant to the east on the island of Qeqertarsuaq (Appendix 2). 32 km to the west lies the next nearest settlement, Upernavik Kujalleq (Søndre Upernavik, 201 inhabitants). The third closest settlement, Kangersuatsiaq (Prøven, 130 inhabitants) lies further to the north. The largest center, the town of Upernavik (1009 inhabitants), is north of the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula. Beyond the roads inside the settlements and town, no roads exist in the Avannaata municipality, including the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula. Typically, to access the peninsula from Upernavik, boats are used in ice-free seasons and snowmobiles or dog sledge when sea ice is present. Since Upernavik has an airport, there exists the possibility of air access to the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula by helicopter or fixed-wing aircraft.

The Sigguup Nunaa is a peninsula extending southwest from the Greenland mainland and located at ca. 71°49'N, 54°25'W. The study area for the count is bounded to the west by Umîarfik Fjord and further west Baffin Bay. To the south is the Ummannaq Fjord system, specifically the Karrats Fjord. To the east the Uvkusigssat Fjord (Ukkusissat Sulluat) separates the peninsula from the glaciated highlands (peak elevations from 1050 m to 2160 m) of Ingia and Akuliarusinguaq, which border the Greenland Ice Cap. The slim northern half of the study area is dominated by steep-sided glacier-covered mountains. The bulbous southern half is also mountainous but has most of the lowlands (Fig. 1). When glaciers (ca. 635 km²) and lakes (ca. 17 km²) are removed, the total study area is ca. 4150 km². The land area with elevations of >200 m is ca. 3010 km² (glaciers, lakes removed). The remaining lowlands, elevations from 0 to 200 m, account for just ca. 1140 km² (lakes removed). The highest elevation within the study area is 1732 m.

Climate on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula is cold. Below-freezing temperatures dominate nine months of every year but can occur anytime. Upernavik, the nearest center with climate data (Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI)) is characterized as Tundra climate. For the 1991-2020 period, mean summer (July) temperatures were from 4°C to 9°C, and mean winter (February-March) temperatures from -22°C to -16°C. Monthly precipitation averages range from 8 mm to 38 mm. Most precipitation falls in the autumn months of September, October, and November. Total annual precipitation is ca. 250 mm and there are ca. 113 days of precipitation annually. The latitude of the peninsula being well above the Arctic Circle (ca. 66.34°N), continuous daylight prevails in summer, the opposite in winter, and minimal sunlight during the early spring and late autumn. The growing season is short, ca. 80-85 days.

Field methods

In 2002, all motorized ground transport on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula was prohibited by law. Thus, dispensation from the Government of Greenland was obtained for the study period, number of vehicles and participants. The ground-based count used four snowmobiles, three of which pulled sledges carrying fuel, gear and provisions. These included the Upernavik hunting officer's snowmobile and sled. The two hunters, Aaron and Roberth, supplied their own snowmobiles and sledges (dogsleds), and the fourth was rented from Upernavik. Before departure, all snowmobiles received mechanical service.

Based on Jens Peter Jørgensen's, Aaron II Karlsen's and Roberth Josvassen's knowledge of muskoxen distribution on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula, all count effort was in the southern half of the study area. The three local participants also determined the daily routes based on terrain features and prevailing weather conditions. A handheld Garmin "etrex legend" GPS device recorded daily routes taken and locations. To avoid counting the same muskox group or individual twice, all routes were counted only once. Animals not immediately visible, e.g. hidden behind terrain features, along a route remained undetected. The minimum count includes only those animals observed.

Figure 14. Observers using binoculars and spotting scopes to find and count muskoxen, April 2002 ground-based minimum count, Sigguup Nunaa peninsula. Photos by C. Cuyler

Muskoxen were located while driving snowmobiles through the terrain. Detecting and counting muskoxen was aided by binoculars (10x magnification, Leica) and spotting scopes (32x-60x magnification, Leica) (Fig. 14). The latter allowed distances between observers and animals of up to about two kilometres, which ensured that the muskoxen did not react with fear to the presence of the observers. Unafraid muskoxen remain spread across the landscape, which makes any calves present readily visible for counting. All four participants functioned as observers and C. Cuyler (GINR) also recorded the data on a field data sheet, which included the date, total number of muskoxen in each group, and whether calves were present (Appendix 3). Calf percent for the population was calculated from the total number observed. We used two age categories, i.e. calve (age < 1-year) and all others (age > 1-year). Body size was the criteria for age, since calves are small-bodied and have almost indiscernible horns

(Olesen & Thing 1989). Sex was not ascertained. Further, every observation was assigned to a grid cell location from the field map (Fig. 15) and specific location marked on that map. GPS locations for muskox groups were approximated from those marks using MapInfo Professional (Version 10.5.2 Pitney Bowes Software), and each muskox group given an ID number in the consecutive order that they were observed.

Figure 15. Field map with 4x4 km grid cells used to record field location of each muskox group observed in 2002.

When observed, we recorded the location of muskox grazing sites, e.g. where muskoxen had dug craters into the snow to find forage. Tracks or the presence of other animals were also recorded.

Appendix 5

Journal of snowmobile problems & field repairs

The four Yamaha snowmobiles had already seen one or several years of use. One was the hunting officer's service vehicle. Two belonged to the commercial hunters and one was a rental. The challenging driving conditions encountered on Sigguup Nunaa during the fieldwork resulted in snowmobiles tipping over while driving and motor/chassis breakdowns. On-the-spot field repairs of the snowmobiles were necessary almost daily, or the minimum count of muskoxen would have had to be abandoned before completion. Once the count effort was finished, all machines required extensive mechanical service, repairs, and parts replacement.

05 April 2002: Just five kilometers out of Upernavik, a short narrow rock-filled gully caused a snowmobile to tip over. This broke the steel sled hitch and the radio antennae that was attached to the snowmobile. Heavy rope secured the sled to the snowmobile thereafter. Duct tape and wrench for support 'fixed' the antenna in place. Meanwhile, the skis of the rented snowmobile wandered and twisted erratically from side-to-side. Only constant brute force kept a steady line of travel. This remained true for the duration of the fieldwork.

06 April 2002: A blizzard reduced visibility down to 20-30 m. Wind gusts were so strong, they flipped heavily loaded sleds over onto their backs twice while driving. The wind combined with the rented snowmobile's erratic ski steering tipped that machine, which bruised the driver. The rental machine uses up fuel too quickly.

07 April 2002: Halfway through today's route, the undercarriage chassis on a commercial hunter's snowmobile came apart and had to be repaired with what we had available (Fig. 16). The rental snowmobile lacked the engine power to climb hillsides and tipped twice. Twice, despite careful driving, the deep soft snow near the location of muskox group number 6, caused a hunter's snowmobile to bog down and tip over.

Figure 16. Repairing the undercarriage of Aaron's snowmobile, 07 April 2002. From left to right, Jens Peter Jørgensen, Aaron II Karlsen (working on snowmobile) and Roberth Jøsvassen.

08 April 2002: No snowmobile problems today (Fig. 17), except that the rental machine continues to burn fuel too quickly and ran out-of-gas twice today. Aaron and Jens made a special trip to Nuugaatsiaq for fuel so that all machines could make it to Nuugaatsiaq today. When we reached Nuugaatsiaq, the undercarriage of Aaron's snowmobile was broken.

Figure 17. Travelling the sea ice, 08 April 2002, with Aaron II Karlsen's and Roberth Josvassen's snowmobiles pulling their sleds using ca. 8-10 m length of rope.

09 April 2002: Before we could depart Nuugaatsiaq, the undercarriage of Aaron's snowmobile required welding repairs. Because of repairs, we departed Nuugaatsiaq at 14:30. Arrived at Remy Jensen's cabin an hour later. Although the sea ice was covered by only 20 cm of powder snow. At the cabin, three of the snowmobiles bogged down in deep (1 m) powder snow.

10 April 2002: This evening, major repairs and many work hours were required on both hunter's snowmobiles. On Roberth's machine, the undercarriage needed repairs to one of the axles and two of the small wheels, one of which had become stuck and stripped its threads. The axel had lost its bolt. We replaced it with another taken from the back rack. However, that bolt was too long, so we needed all the large sized washers that Jens (Aqqaluk) had brought with him to make it tight.

Further, the rental snowmobile was getting worse to steer, as the skis twist violently. We repaired the left ski by hammering somewhat straight the badly bent steering rod that runs almost the length of the ski base. (Obviously, the bent steering rods should have been replaced with new ones before the fieldwork began.) Also, a part in the rental's undercarriage suspension had broken, so we made a temporary fix by tying it back together with binder twine.

Figure 18. Extra wide plastic skis (pink) attached under the snowmobile's regular skis. Photo by C. Cuyler.

11 April 2002: Deep powder snow in the Qiterdlikavsak valley bogged down three of the four snowmobiles. Only the machine with the extra wide plastic skis (Fig. 18) could get into this valley. By late afternoon, the undercarriage of Hunting Officer's snowmobile broke apart. It could not pull its sled but made it back to Upernavik Kujalleq. The rental machine pulled the sled.

12 April 2002: The undercarriage of Hunting Officer's snowmobile needed welding repairs before we could head out today. On the first day of the fieldwork, the steel hitch for the sled broke. Thereafter the sled was affixed to the snowmobile with rope. Driving over stone-hard blown snow created repeated pull, push and slam of the sled into the rear undercarriage, so now some pieces of the undercarriage were shattered, and the belt flap ruined. Today, it was 14:00 before repairs were completed and we could leave to count muskoxen. After driving in the mountainous terrain surrounding the Mitdlôrfik Fjord, the undercarriage of Roberth's snowmobile broke and had to be repaired to make possible the return trip to Upernavik Kujalleq (Fig. 19). This required 1½ hours. Further, by the end of today's work, Aaron's snowmobile undercarriage broke apart, which would need welding to repair.

Figure 19. Repairs and refuelling before returning to Upernavik Kujalleq, 12 April 2002. Photo by C. Cuyler.

13 April 2002: Welding the undercarriage of Aaron’s snowmobile took all morning before repair was completed. Just as we were ready to depart Upernavik Kujalleq for the return trip to Upernavik, Robert’s snowmobile motor would not run. Thus, we started the drive to Upernavik at 12:25 with only three snowmobiles (Fig. 20).

Figure 20. Two of the Yamaha snowmobiles used for the April 2002 muskox minimum count on Sigguup Nunaa. Photo by C. Cuyler

Appendix 6

Sea ice route between Upernavik and Upernavik Kujalleq - 13 April 2002

The sea ice route between the town of Upernavik and settlement of Upernavik Kujalleq was usually about a two-hour snowmobile drive when driving conditions were good. On the 13th of April 2002, however, travel time increased to four hours and 15 minutes, owing to poor ice conditions and troubles getting sleds up or down difficult hills (i.e. sleds tipping and/or snowmobiles bogging down) (Fig. 21).

Figure 21. Sea route between Upernavik and Upernavik Kujalleq on the 13th of April 2002, illustrating the various difficulties encountered and where those occurred.

Appendix 7

How to document possible wolverine tracks

Since 2002, GINR has received several reports from Avannaata (Upernavik) locals that wolverines (Fig. 22) are inhabiting the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula. To the date of this publication, no conclusive documentation has been obtained. To facilitate useful photographic documentation of animal tracks, the following guidelines are provided, and apply to all animal tracks, not just to those of the wolverine.

Figure 22. Photograph of a Norwegian wolverine, member of the Mustelidae family that resembles a small bear. Photo by Arild Landa.

1. When outdoors, always have a camera/cell-phone handy.
2. A measuring tool, e.g. a measuring stick (as pictured in Fig. 24) or a tape measure is necessary. Lay the measuring tool alongside the animal tracks. If you lack a measuring tool, place alongside the animal tracks something of a known size, e.g. Tordenskjold brand matchstick box (common in Greenland) or a cigarette lighter. The exact size of either can be measured later.
3. Always take photographs of single paw prints with a measuring tool alongside. Always take photographs of both the front and back feet.

Note: The front foot is always **bigger** than the back foot, and the back foot paw print can lie on top of the front foot's print.

4. The length and pattern of a series of animal tracks is often essential for ascertaining what animal made the track. Therefore, stand back and take photographs of the track pattern itself, i.e. get as many footprints in the picture as possible.
5. Since track patterns vary with the animal's gait (walking, trotting, running), get photographic documentation of every gait you discover. Photos of several different gaits from the same animal provide good evidence for what species made the tracks, even when the individual paw prints are indistinct.
6. Regarding the different gaits, it is important to measure the distance between each 'set' of prints and the length of each 'set'. Write down the distance between sets and record which distance measurement belongs to each photo. Wolverines often use a loping running gait to cover large open spaces. Then, their tracks often appear at an angle because the animal moves diagonally across the landscape. This creates track sequences that are in 'sets' of three prints (Fig 23, A), each print about the size of a large dog. The middle print is made by two paws.

Less common, wolverines may bounce, making track sequences with 'sets' of 2 prints (Fig. 23, B). Depending on how fast the wolverine is moving, wolverine track sequences can also be in sets of 4 like that of a dog or wolf.

Figure 23. Two different track sequences common to wolverine: Sets of three prints, the diagonal loping gait(A), and sets of two prints as the wolverine bounces through snow (B).

7. IMPORTANT, regarding wolverines...their **front paws have five (5) toes**, can be ≥ 11.5 cm long, the foot pad is chevron (\wedge) shaped, and a heel can be present further behind the chevron foot pad (Fig. 24). All five (5) toes and claws are usually visible in the paw print. Toes are asymmetrically arranged. When the substrate is new snow or soft soil/mud, IF you cannot see five (5) toes then it

is NOT a wolverine track. Of course, on hard ground, ice or hard crust snow, the small 5th lateral 'thumb' toe often will not show up in the front paw print. When this happens, the track pattern (see 4.), becomes critical for ascertaining what species made the tracks.

Note: canids, e.g. foxes, wolves, and dogs, have only four (4) toes in their paw prints, since their 5th toe is high up on the leg and never touches the ground/snow. Further, unlike wolverines a canid's 4 toes are arranged symmetrically, and the foot pad is not chevron shaped.

Figure 24. Size and shape of wolverine (Gulo gulo) tracks, front paw (below) & rear paw (above), with former clearly illustrating the characteristic five (5) toes, chevron (\wedge) shaped foot pad, and small heel. Note also asymmetric arrangement of the toes and the lateral position of the hind toe. Further, there is the appearance of a rearmost heel of the foot. Photo courtesy of Roy Anderson, NINA (Norwegian Institute for Nature Research).

8. Always take many photos. Take them from different angles and vary the distance from close-ups to landscape photographs.

Appendix 8

Photographs from April 2002 field work for muskox minimum count on the Sigguup Nunaa peninsula

Figure 25. Participants from the Avannata municipality for 2002 minimum count, above left – Aaron II Karlsen (Commercial hunter, Upernavik Kujalleq); above centre – Roberth Jovassen (Commercial hunter, Upernavik Kujalleq); above right – Jens Peter Jørgensen (Upernavik hunting officer). Photos by C. Cuyler.

Figure 26. View north into one of the five valleys on the southern coast of Sigguup Nunaa peninsula. Photo by C. Cuyler.

Figure 27. An iceberg frozen in the sea ice of Karrats Fjord, with Aaron II Karlsen driving his snowmobile and towing dog sled in the foreground. Photo by C. Cuyler.

Figure 28. South-facing mountainside on the north side of Amitsup suvdlua Fjord, illustrating the blue frozen waterfalls typical for Sigguaup Nunaa mountain slopes in early April 2002. Photo by C. Cuyler.

Fig. 29. Solar halo over the flat mountain top, Sigguaup Nunaa, 11 April 2002. Photo by C. Cuyler

Figure 30. An ice berg frozen into the sea ice offshore from the town of Upernavik. Photo by C. Cuyler

Figure 31. Last evening of the Sigguup Nunaa muskox minimum count, 12 April 2002. Photo by C. Cuyler

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